

ARTISTIC DRAWINGS ON THE FIGURE OF THE CREATOR

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Abstract. *The structure of an autobiographical and biographical work, the composition of the work, is fundamentally different from memories. In them, events related to the life of the author are described on the basis of a certain system. And in the memoirs, a short period of the life of a particular person is told, which remains in the speaker's memory. In an autobiographical work, events acquire a certain final completion. The memoir covers short events. They can be called an excerpt from a large-scale work.*

Keywords: *author's "me", memories, memorabilia, memoirs and diaries, biographical work, autobiographical work, vitality, artistry, personal experience, style.*

Introduction. Autobiographical works are not only important sources of information about the life and activities of a particular writer, but also about the era they lived in. Literary scholar O. Toshboyev interprets the creation of Oybek's "Bolalik xotiralarim" (My Childhood Memories) as follows: "Bolalik xotiralarim" is one of Oybek's unfinished works, an expression of his gratitude towards respected individuals who told stories of glorious history, his eternal sorrow, and his repentance... This regret stems from his mentors who said, 'Honor the scholars, think about religion and the afterlife, the scholars are the only true leaders of the people'; and also the influence of Tavalloyu Bekhbudi, Chulpon, and Munavvarqori on him. Indeed, such a troubled state is inevitable for every person, especially for the writer, whose heart is illuminated by the light of faith. When the author reflects on his half-century life, he regrets the suffering of soldiers, the malicious actions of those who became corrupt in the country, the unfulfilled hopes of swords left in the grave, and the cries of workers who perished in the North. This regret and feeling of indebtedness were eventually transformed into "Bolalik xotiralarim."

Analysis of thematic literature. The correctness of the scholar's views is confirmed by Abdulla Qakhhor's thoughts on autobiographical writings. "Like many" wrote A. Qakhhor, "I was puzzled about what 'writing' really meant and how personal experiences and impressions could serve as valuable material for literary works. After understanding this, what I saw and experienced in my childhood began to look different. The past, like wine in a deep cellar, becomes clearer in memory over time. The longer the time passes, the clearer and stronger the wine becomes. Similarly, the experiences from my youth are the purest and strongest memories that will never fade. These impressions from the past later became the foundation for many of my stories and episodes in my major works."

"Fairy Tales from the Past" was a distinctive culmination of the writer's creative journey. It is an autobiographical work that reflects the author's childhood experiences, but it sharply contrasts with other autobiographical works in Uzbek literature, such as Oybek's "Bolalik" (Childhood) novella. In Oybek's novella, the image of the child takes central stage, while in "Fairy Tales from the Past," Abdullakh's image as a child takes a backseat; he is mainly portrayed as an observer, a witness, and an impartial narrator. The author's main focus is on the events in the family and around the family, witnessed by the child. In the novella, the writer remains a

storyteller, with almost every chapter, except for the last one, “Among the Ruins of Kokand,” being a complete story, tragic in nature. The novella echoes the author’s final lament about human dignity, the pain of injustices, and rebellion against ignorance.

Uzbek national poet Anvar Obidjon, in his novella “Roads with evil spirits” (There Are Worn Paths), reflects on his childhood memories and life experiences, particularly recalling his father: “Although my father could read and write in Arabic, Latin, and Cyrillic scripts with ease, he was indifferent to secular knowledge and politics. Especially, as a descendant of the eshon family, his lack of expertise in religious knowledge surprised many”.

In the book “Analysis – The Way to Understanding Literature” by scholar Qunduzoy Khusanboyeva, she mentions autobiographical works found in school textbooks, stating: “In the sixth-grade ‘Literature’ textbook, there is a brief account of the life and work of the great writer Odil Yoqubov. The story ‘Muzqaymoq’ (Ice Cream) that should be studied also has an autobiographical character, similar to Erkin Vokhidov’s poem ‘Nido’ (The Call). For this reason, the article is assigned as homework at the end of the previous lesson. During the first lesson, some time is spent on unveiling the author’s personality and forming an understanding of his difficult childhood years”.

Research methodology. Autobiographical works are not only important sources of information about a specific writer’s life and activities, but also about the period in which they lived. Literary scholar O. Toshboyev interprets the creation of Oybek’s “My Childhood Memories” as follows: “My Childhood Memories” is one of Oybek’s unfinished works, a reflection of his regret and reverence for the honorable people of history, offering an apology and expressing an endless longing. This apology is directed towards his mentors who taught him to respect scholars, think about the afterlife, and guided the people with wisdom; it also expresses gratitude to figures like Tavalloyu Bekhbudiy, Chulpon, and Munavvarqori. Indeed, this painful feeling is something every believer, especially a writer, experiences. As the author reflects on his half-century life, he regrets not being able to reconcile with the pain of the soldiers, the misdeeds of the ‘mochalov’ (heretics), and the unfortunate fates of those who perished. This sense of regret and indebtedness finds its expression in “My Childhood Memories”[1].

The validity of this view is confirmed by Abdulla Qahhor’s thoughts on autobiographical writings. He writes, “Like many others, I struggled to understand what ‘writing’ meant, and that personal experiences and impressions can be incredibly valuable materials for literary works. After I realized this, the things I saw as a child, the people I met, and the events of my youth appeared in a different light. The past, like wine in a deep cellar, becomes clearer over time; the more time passes, the more refined and stronger the memories become, and the experiences of youth remain the purest and most powerful memories that never fade.” These impressions of the past later became the foundation of many of his stories and episodes in his major works[2].

“Fairy Tales from the Past” is the author’s distinctive conclusion and the final peak of his work. The autobiographical nature of “Fairy Tales from the Past” is different from other Uzbek autobiographical works, such as Oybek’s “Childhood” story. In Oybek’s work, the child character is central, whereas in “Fairy Tales from the Past,” the image of the child, Abdullah, is secondary. He is mainly a “witness” or “observer,” with the writer’s focus being on the events that occurred within the family. The narrative retains its storytelling nature, except for the last chapter, “Among the Ruins of Kokand,” where every chapter is essentially a completed tragic novella. In this work,

feelings and thoughts related to the honor and dignity of a person, and a rebellion against ignorance, echo as the writer's final outcry[3].

Uzbek poet Anvar Obidjon, in his "Ajinasi bor yo'llar" (The Road with Evil Spirits), reflects on childhood memories and life experiences, remembering his father: "My father, although he could read and write easily in Arabic, Latin, and Cyrillic scripts, was indifferent to worldly knowledge and politics. Especially considering that he came from a family of religious scholars, his lack of knowledge in religious matters surprised many"[4].

In her book "Analysis – The Way to Understand Literature," scholar Qunduzoy Khusanboyeva discusses autobiographical works found in school literature textbooks. She states: "In the sixth grade 'Literature' textbook, a brief introduction to the life and work of the great writer Odil Yoqubov is provided. The story 'Ice Cream,' just like Erkin Vokhidov's poem 'Nido,' has a somewhat autobiographical character. Therefore, reading this article is assigned as homework after the previous lesson. In the first lesson, a little time is spent on the author's personality, focusing on his difficult childhood years".

It is advisable to focus students' attention on the historical context in "Ice Cream," examining the injustice and cruelty that took place during the writer's childhood, which significantly shaped his personal development and fate as a writer[5].

Observing the "Literature" textbooks shows that the portrayal of the writer's childhood and growing years is very brief, making it difficult to understand his personality, inner world, and ideals. The events that defined the writer's fate during his childhood or schooling years may significantly influence the formation of the reader's personality[6].

Analysis and results. There are many autobiographical writings in Uzbek literature. When comparing autobiographies and memoirs, the following distinctions become clear. Autobiographical works are mainly created by people engaged in artistic creation, while memoirs are written by people of various professions. In autobiographical works, artistic style is prominent, and expressive means, such as description and literary techniques, are frequently used. In memoirs, a conversational style is more noticeable, with the narration leading the structure. In autobiographical works, a literary portrait of the individual is created, while memoirs usually provide only partial information.

In autobiographies, work is often based on documents. Historical accuracy, clarity, and documentation are key features of autobiographies. Although focused on depicting real life and specific individuals, autobiographical works demand artistic excellence and aesthetic unity. When discussing the artistry of such works, Professor D. Qurono's thoughts are relevant: "The more abundant the biographical material (documents related to the writer's life and activities, information about the environment and interactions with people, his correspondence, memoirs about him, etc.), the more effective the application of the method. Of course, biographical material is never completely exhaustive, meaning it is difficult to reconstruct the writer's life on a day-to-day documentary basis. Therefore, biographical material aims to bring life to facts and fill in missing gaps, which may involve introducing hypothetical elements"[7].

Conclusions and suggestions. When studying a literary work and determining its content, artistic intent, narrative skill, and aesthetic concepts, information related to the author's personality is of significant importance. The lives and works of creators are naturally studied in connection with the historical and literary environment of their time. Professor Qozokboy Yuldoshev's observations on literary analysis address this issue, noting that comparing an author with their

contemporaries, relatives, fans, and even rivals can bring students closer to understanding the author's personality, encouraging them to take inspiration from them.

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